

Support stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9

Deliverable 3.5 Develop presentation
materials and give presentations at external
conferences

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1 INTRODUCTION

This report is an overview of the presentations that the ZEP/IWG9 secretariat gave at external conferences to ensure that conclusions and recommendations from IWG9 and ETIP ZEP are widely disseminated also to broader stakeholders.

1.1 Development of presentation materials

The secretariat developed a standard slide deck that could be used for different audiences, touching upon topics such as:

- A) Explanation of the ZEP and IWG9
- B) Overview of CCS technologies (and their importance)
- C) Current policy developments and challenges
- D) Growth of the CCS market

The presentations were always adapted to the audience to make the content as relevant as possible. The slides were made publicly available by the event organisers (if they requested this to the secretariat, this was always confirmed). Content was also checked regularly with the ZEP Chair and members to ensure the factual correctness and include the latest information.

1.2 External presentations in 2022-2025

In Annex A is an overview of the external presentations that the ZEP/IWG9 secretariat gave during the lifetime of the project. Most of these presentations were keynotes on conferences, focusing on EU policy and market developments of CCS and CCU, with attendees already having a varying degree of knowledge on these topics but willing to learn more. Included are also presentations that were given at events organised by the European Commission, these are also mentioned in Deliverable 3.3.

ANNEX A: OVERVIEW OF EXTERNAL PRESENTATIONS DURING THE PROJECT

Meeting	Date	ZEP/ IWG9 Representative	Organisation	Topic of ZEP presentation / Role of speaker
ONS Conference 2022	31 August 2022	Per-Olof Granström	ONS	Organisation of session: “Carbon dioxide removal - enabling negative emissions”
ACCSESS Open Oslo Event	22 September 2022	Per-Olof Granström	ACCSESS	Keynote: Making CCS a success story – state of play and the road ahead
7th H2O20 CCUS Alternative fuels workshop	September 2022	Per-Olof Granström	CINEA	Presentation of ZEP/IWG9 and SET Plan targets
CCUS Forum 2022	27-28 October 2022	Per-Olof Granström	European Commission	Moderator
16 th SET Plan Conference	9 November 2022	Marie Bysveen	SET PLAN	Information about IWG9 work at SET Plan conference Title: ‘Towards a new Strategic Energy Technology Plan’
CCUS Forum 2022	28 November 2022	Eve Tamme	European Commission	Panellist, Session: All hands on deck: establishing industrial initiative on CCS and CCU
Climit Summit 2023	8 January 2023	Per-Olof Granström	Climit	Introduction to CCS in Europe
CETP strategy meeting	10 January 2023	Marie Bysveen	CETP	Input from IWG9 to CETP scoping Title: ‘CETP 2023 Scoping meeting TRI3 on CCUS’
Baltic seminar	1 March 2023	Eve Tamme	Ccs4cee.eu	Updates and position of CCS in the Baltic states

Meeting	Date	ZEP/ IWG9 Representative	Organisation	Topic of ZEP presentation / Role of speaker
IEAGHG Webinar	7 June 2023	Marie Bysveen	IEA	Informing global CCUS actors about SET Plan and European collaboration Title: 'The role of RD&D in the commercial deployment of CCS'
European Sustainable Energy Week	22 June 2023	Eve Tamme	European Commission	Session: Climate neutral Europe: safeguarding jobs and industrial competitiveness Panellist to discuss the potential of CCS in enabling a just transition to net-zero
European Sustainable Energy Week	20-22 June 2023	Per-Olof Granström	European Commission	Organiser of session: The skills and cost of industrial decarbonisation. Opening presentation: The key steps for successful deployment of CCUS in Europe
series '10 Experts, 10 Ideas, One Goal	17-24 September 2023	Kristin Jordal	Drax	Video at NY Climate Week on BECCS and carbon removal
8th H2020 CCUS/Alternative fuels workshop	20 September 2023	Joop Hazenberg	CINEA	Presentation of SSZEPIWG9 project and link to Horizon Europe work on CCS
Greenshift CCUS Summit	21 September 2023	Joop Hazenberg	SINTEF / Norwegian embassies	Panellist on EU CCS policies
EU Industry Days	5 October 2023	Eve Tamme	European Commission	Session organised by ZEP and Global CCS Institute Topic: Decarbonising with Carbon Capture and Storage: A Pathway to Green Transformation and Industrial Competitiveness Eve Tamme moderated

Meeting	Date	ZEP/ IWG9 Representative	Organisation	Topic of ZEP presentation / Role of speaker
7th ACT Knowledge Sharing Workshop	5 October 2023	Joop Hazenberg	ACT	Keynote on EU CCS policy and market developments
CCUS Conference London – Springboard to Net Zero	18 October 2023	Eve Tamme	CCSA	Panellist, session: EU CDR policies
Eurogas Tech conference	26 October 2023	Eve Tamme	Eurogas	Panellist, Session: European Leadership in Bioenergy with carbon capture and storage and pyrolysis
Carbon Capture: A Big Decarbonization Enabler	26 October 2023	Joop Hazenberg	Tecnicas Reunidas / Global CCS Institute	Keynote on EU CCS policy and market developments
Hydrogen Leadership Forum	14 December 2023	Joop Hazenberg	Management Producties	Moderator of working group CCS & blue hydrogen
Clean Energy Transition Partnership strategy meeting	9 January 2024	Marie Bysveen	CETP	Engage CETP stakeholders in the IWG9 R&I update process Title: 'Strategic discussion on CCUS 2024'
The Development of CCS in the EEA	30 January 2024	Eve Tamme	EFTA Surveillance Authority	Moderation of panel
CCUS ZEN Madrid Event	21 February 2024	Joop Hazenberg	CCUS ZEN	Keynote on EU CCS policy and market developments
Clean Transition Dialogue on clean tech	22 February 2024	Joop Hazenberg	European Commission	Participant in roundtable with President von der Leyen, intervention on importance of CCS/CCU

Meeting	Date	ZEP/ IWG9 Representative	Organisation	Topic of ZEP presentation / Role of speaker
Clean Transition Dialogue on steel industry	22 March 2024	Joop Hazenberg	European Commission	Participant in roundtable with Vice-Presidents Vestager and Sefcovic, intervention on CCS for steel industry
EERA JP CCS Webinar	16 February 2024	Marie Bysveen	EERA	Engage stakeholders in the IWG9 R&I update process Title: 'Industrial Carbon Management Strategy and SET Plan update'
GCCSI Europe Forum	17 April 2024	Eadbhard Pernot	Global CCS Institute	Moderation of panel
CCS Network Meeting	30 May 2024	Eve Tamme	Swedish Energy Agency	Keynote speech
JEF-IPCEI - Clean tech working group	16 September 2024	Eadbhard Pernot	Young European Federalists	Presentation on advanced materials
JEF-IPCEI – Clean tech working group	23 September 2024	Eadbhard Pernot	Young European Federalists	Presentation on an IPCEI for Industrial Carbon Management
Northern Lights Celebration: Ready for CO2	26 September 2024	Eadbhard Pernot	Northern Lights	Keynote on Creating permanent carbon removals in Europe
ICM Forum 2024	13 October 2024	Eadbhard Pernot	European Commission	Panel moderation, session "How to approach CO2 standardisation in an emerging market?"
CCS Europe Breakfast Event	26 November 2024	Eadbhard Pernot	CCS Europe	Keynote
Politico Sustainable Future Week	3 December 2024	Eadbhard Pernot	Politico Europe	Panellist, session "carbon crunch time: removals, storage, can Europe have it all?"
SCCS Annual Conference	3 December 2024	Aymeric Amand	Scotland CCS	Keynote

Meeting	Date	ZEP/ IWG9 Representative	Organisation	Topic of ZEP presentation / Role of speaker
ETIPs Forum Meeting	13 December 2024	Eadbhard Pernot	Zabala and EERA	Presentation on ZEP and its business model
ACT3 RETURN Project - Final workshop	17 December 2024	Eadbhard Pernot	SINTEF	Keynote speech "Carbon management under the next EU Commission: What to expect"
Going back to basics - Industrial Carbon Management: Carbon Capture, Utilisation, Storage and Removals	16 January 2025	Aymeric Amand	European Energy Forum	Presentation "Direct Air Capture: an overview" Panellist, session "Carbon Removal: Exploring BECCS and CDR/DAC solutions"
ACCSESS Open Brussels Event – The Clean Industrial Deal: working together for a vibrant European industry and a decarbonised society	29 January 2025	Aymeric Amand	SINTEF	Keynote speech "CCS Status in Europe"
The Economist Carbon Capture Summit	6 February 2025	Eve Tamme	The Economist	Panellist, session "Carbon to cash: can carbon capture be profitable"
European CCUS Webinar series	24 February 2025	Aymeric Amand	UK CCS Research Centre	Presentation "European CCS policy landscape"
CLIMIT Summit 2025	25 February 2025	Marie Bysveen	CLIMIT	Inform stakeholders about status of IWG9 R&I update (D1.4). Title: 'European CCUS R&I landscape'

Meeting	Date	ZEP/ IWG9 Representative	Organisation	Topic of ZEP presentation / Role of speaker
Climit Summit 2025	25 February 2025	Aymeric Amand	GASSNOVA	Presentation on “Breaking Carbon Boundaries: Europe's Competitiveness in CCS Research and Development”
CATO Spring Summit, The Netherlands	3 March 2025	Marie Bysveen	CATO	Inform stakeholders about status of IWG9 R&I update. Title: ‘EERA JP CCS and a European plan for CCUS R&I’
Clean Energy Transition Partnership (CETP) Strategy meeting	11 March 2025	Marie Bysveen	CETP	Give input to upcoming CETP call. Title: ‘European plan for CCUS R&I’
2025 Europe Forum on Carbon Capture and Storage	19 March 2025	Eve Tamme	Global CCSI Institute	Panellist, session: “CCS Development in the EU and Beyond”
Leveraging CO ₂ in the Circular Carbon Economy	8 May 2025	Aymeric Amand	ERCST	Panellist, session on EU policies and standardisation
CCS Conference 2025	26 May 2025	Eadbhard Pernot	DTU Offshore	Keynote speech on the CCUS EU Policy Landscape
CCUS Conference Norway	11 June 2025	Eadbhard Pernot	Energy Transition Norway; Stavanger Chamber of Commerce; the ONS Foundation; Municipality of Stavanger	Keynote speech on the CCUS EU Policy Landscape
Trondheim CCS Conference	17 June 2025	Eve Tamme	NCCS, gigaCCS, SINTEF, NTNU	Keynote speech

ANNEX B: EXAMPLE OF PRESENTATION MATERIAL

The EU landscape for CCS & CCU
Updates & Expectations

26 October 2023 - Madrid

Zero Emissions Platform

CCS and CCU projects in Europe

More than 70 market-ready CCS and CCU projects looking to become operational by 2030.

Porthos CCS project to start construction in 2024 and become operational by 2026.

Northern Light project located in Norway to start operations in 2024.

Implications of large-scale CCS and CCU

- **Theoretical CO2 storage capacity in EEA:** 262-1520 GtCO₂/year
- **Current industrial emissions in EEA:** 780 MtCO₂/year
- **Maximum industrial CCS in EEA:** 520 MtCO₂/year
- **Additional non-industrial CCS (hydrogen, biomass...):** 720 MtCO₂/year
- **To be consistent with the 1.5° goal of the Paris Agreement, the EU needs by 2030:**
 - 230-430 MtCO₂/yr of CO₂ removals in 2030
 - 930-1200 MtCO₂/yr of CO₂ removals by 2050
 - EUR 14 billion/yr in CCS and CCU investments
- **CCS and CCU are key to preserving the over 8 million jobs in hard-to-abate sectors in Europe** while creating new value chains and jobs

Zero Emissions Platform – who we are

The **Zero Emissions Platform (ZEP)** is a European Technology and Innovation Platform (ETIP) under the **European Strategic Energy Technology Plan (SET-Plan)**.

The EU advisory body on CCS and CCU deployment and development.

ZEP unites a diverse range of stakeholders from oil and gas companies, hard-to-abate industries, researchers and environmental NGOs.

 ZEP is supported by the European Union and receives funding from Horizon Europe (grant n°101075790)

Zero Emissions Platform - mission

- 1 Create the right conditions to reach net-zero by 2050 focusing on energy and industrial sectors.
- 2 Demonstrate that the implementation of CCS and some applications of CCU technologies are essential to this goal.
- 3 Accelerate the deployment of large-scale CO2 transport and storage networks.

How to make it possible?

- Development of European CO2 transport and storage infrastructure
- An enabling policy framework making it economically feasible to invest in CCS and CCU
- Incentives to support large -scale deployment of all parts along the CCUS value chain
- Strong continued support for CCUS Research and Innovation

2023 – a pivotal year for CCS

- **March 2023 - Net-Zero Industry Act proposal**
 - Focus on CO2 injection capacity
 - Objective of **50 Mtpa by 2030 CO2 storage capacity**
 - Member States to build up capacity: Reporting on storage and project progress
 - Faster permitting – up to 18 months, less administrative burden.
 - Currently under negotiation - expected to be adopted in 2024.
- **June 2023 - National Energy and Climate Plans**
 - EU Member States strategy to achieve nationally determined climate targets.
 - Spain NECP submitted in July 2023.
 - EU Member States NECPs with ambitious CCS strategies: Denmark, the Netherlands, Italy.
 - Expecting France, Germany, Belgium,...

More to come in 2024...

- **Monitoring reporting regulation – revision of ETS with Fit For 55 – Q1 2024**
 - 4th Amendment Act of the EU ETS
 - Expected amendments on CCS and CCU (including CO2 transport)
- **EU Industrial Carbon Management Strategy – Q1 2024**
 - Dedicated regulatory framework for CO2 transport and storage.
 - CCUS Forum WGs – ZEP co-chairs WG on CO2 infrastructure
 - CCUS Forum in Denmark 27-28 November – to guide the strategy